

DELIVERABLE D6.1

Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

EMPOWER

*“Uptake of new generation AI Powered Investigative tools
for Law Enforcement Agencies”*

Call topic: DIGITAL-2022-DEPLOY-02-LAW-SECURITY-AI

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About EMPOWER

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The application of AI methods to Big Data heralds a new era in Law Enforcement, increasing the operational capabilities of Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) in fighting and predicting crime in a wide number of investigative domains, including the fight against Child Sexual Exploitation (CSE), Terrorism, Cybercrime and the protection of Public Spaces.

Promising technological solutions and tools are being developed within the framework of EU and nationally funded R&I projects reaching TRL 6 to 7 and applicable to a wide number of investigative fields. Building up from such previous and ongoing R&I projects, the overall goal of EMPOWER is to foster the uptake of innovative solutions based upon AI powered tools allowing Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) to increase their capabilities in such investigative fields.

To that end, EMPOWER will pilot test a total of 8 investigative tools in the fields of Image/Video, Voice/Text and Federated Learning, in a concerted effort carried out by the consortium. As a result of the project, 8 tools will be brought to TRL 8 level, following their testing by LEAs in real-life environments.

Such tools will be made available to other non-partner LEAs through open repositories and licensing schemes in coordination with key players. Lastly, anonymised data sets, a training needs analysis, training materials and recommendations on the following will also be widely disseminated:

- i) Data Interoperability and standardisation,
- ii) AI Trustworthiness of LEA tools, and
- iii) The Innovation Uptake models of new AI based solutions by LEAs.

EMPOWER Project Participants:

[[TGO](#)] [[MIR-PN](#)] [[PJ](#)] [[HERTA](#)] [[ICTLC](#)] [[SLG](#)] [[CERTH](#)] [[TREBE](#)] [[VICOM](#)] [[VOI](#)]

Executive Summary

This document provides a detailed description of EMPOWER project's orientation towards communication, dissemination and exploitation. This deliverable situates the EMPOWER project in the ecosystem of EC funded projects in this domain and outlines a bespoke approach to communicating with law enforcement stakeholders and other relevant organisations. The EMPOWER project has as its focus the adoption of AI based investigative tools for those LEA personnel engaged in the fight against child sexual exploitation. This is reflected in our communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies. EMPOWER seeks to leverage its relationship with *innovation brokers* in order to improve uptake of toolsets created in a number of recently completed and ongoing EC funded projects in this field. Furthermore, as part of the dissemination / exploitation piece, EMPOWER will produce training material to improve capacity of LEAs operating in this area.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

CEPOL	European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Training
CoU	Community of Users
CSE	Child Sexual Exploitation
CSEM	Child Sexual Exploitation Material
EACTDA	European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association
ECTEG	European Cybercrime Training and Education Group
ENLETS	The European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services
ERT	Europol Repository of Tools
FCT	Fighting Crime and Terrorism
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency
NCMEC	National Center for Missing and Exploited Children
SO	Strategic Objective
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

In March of 2023, at a European Commission workshop on the future use of AI for security purposes, DG HOME Director Marta Cygan emphasised the potential AI tools have in assisting law enforcement authorities when investigating terrorist content online or for combatting child sexual abuse¹. For this potential to be realised, effective training and dissemination regimes will be required. EMPOWER will play an important role in helping to leverage the power of AI based technologies for European law enforcement. This plan will provide detail on communication, dissemination and exploitation goals and define specific messages for each goal identified. This report will also draft a stakeholder analysis of target groups in this domain. This analysis, combined with the identification of relevant communication channels, materials, activities and tools for each goal, will clarify appropriate communication strategies to be used in each case. Each goal will be considered within a balanced scorecard framework. In line with the overall aim of the balanced scorecard, this will ensure the measurement of success throughout EMPOWER considers several perspectives. It will also remove the risk of too narrow a focus for the project as the variability in assessment from different stakeholder groups will be considered. Communication and dissemination in this domain represents a particular challenge given the nature of stakeholders inherent to the field and the sensitive nature of work carried out in this investigative arena. Thus, TGO and consortium partners have designed a bespoke approach to communication, dissemination and exploitation that will target key stakeholders and maximise practice impact. To this end, a number of deliverables produced as part of EMPOWER will remain classified as 'Sensitive' and shared with a small group of specified stakeholders.

¹ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/news/ceris-workshop-use-artificial-intelligence-security-purposes-2023-03-29_en

2 Strategy and Objectives

The objectives for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation within EMPOWER reflect priorities of the key sectors engaged in this project. The prevalence of AI brings opportunities for LEA's to enhance efficiency in their fight against crime and terrorism, specifically for this project, in the area of CSE. An awareness of the tools that exist and the ability to use these tools are necessary before any upsides can be taken advantage of. The importance of robust training regimes for law enforcement in the use of AI continued to be emphasised by key stakeholders². In order for AI tool development within the EU to remain sustainable and to continue their innovations, it is necessary that a market exists for these tools. Of similar importance to tool developers is the need for feedback and end user evaluations in order to perfect their solutions and ensure they are market ready. All of these goals are only achievable through some level of communication, dissemination and exploitation. The key objectives for this plan will be linked to the overall strategic objectives of the project demonstrating the high degree of integration of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities throughout the entire project and the high degree of engagement between EMPOWER and external stakeholders.

2.1 Communication

A key goal is to communicate with stakeholders the following aspects of EMPOWER: the project goals, the consortium composition, the overall social benefits, and the contributions to the European digital, security, industrial and AI strategies. The purpose of this communication is threefold; in the early stages of the project the intention is to attract collaborators. Engagement with external collaborators such as EACTDA, CEPOL, ECTEG and Europol has the potential to enhance the exploitation capability of EMPOWER as this project can build on the progress made to date. As part of EMPOWER networking with relevant related projects (funded by DEP, ISF-P, H2020 and HE), networking events and associations in the FCT field will take place with the aim of advancing in the area of interoperability standards and indeed the further uptake of the tested solutions.

During the project, as the demonstration events take place, EMPOWER will communicate with external stakeholders with the purpose of generating demand amongst the LEA community and beyond for the solutions being demonstrated. Finally, during the later stages of the project the focus of communication activities will be on presenting the successes of the project and the utility of tools developed to relevant communities.

Communication activities will be integrated with all other activities throughout the project. The overall strategic objectives of EMPOWER tightly linked with the communication plan include:

- SO5. TRANSFER. To promote the uptake and adoption of the tested tools by the 2 partner LEAs and by the wider EU LEA community by the means of demonstrating the impact on the use of the tools networking with relevant projects and initiatives such as H2020 and HE projects, Europol Innovation Lab, EU Centre to fight child abuse, ENLETS, EACTDA, etc.

² See Coman, I. and Alexa, N., 2022. EU Law Enforcement Training Needs on Digital Skills and the Use of New Technologies. European Law Enforcement Research Bulletin, (22).

- Responds to Activity A5 and A6 of the Call Fiche.
- Addressed in WP2 and WP6.
- KPIs: KB6: 40 communication and dissemination activities (workshops, events, bilateral meetings, publications).

Without communication regarding the impact the tools can have on the investigative abilities of LEAs it would be impossible to expect the wider EU LEA community to adopt these solutions. It is therefore necessary for SO5 success that communication takes place in the form of the promotion of the uptake of these tools.

- SO6. RECOMMENDATIONS. To disseminate guidelines and recommendations in order i) to ensure the ethical AI trustworthiness of AI based investigative tools, ii) advance in the interoperability and standardisation of datasets and iii) share success stories and the models followed for the adoption and uptake by LEAs of innovative technologies and solutions.
 - Responds to Activity A4, A5 and A6 of the Call Fiche.
 - Addressed in WP2, WP4 and WP6. Call: DIGITAL-2022-DEPLOY-02-LAW-SECURITY-AI - Security (law enforcement): AI-based pilot 6
 - KPI: KB6: 40 communication and dissemination activities (workshops, events, bilateral meetings, publications).

Communicating recommendations that are established as part of the EMPOWER project will support other SO's in their use and adoption of these AI solutions allowing for more efficient uptake and more effective use.

2.2 Dissemination

The aim of EMPOWER's dissemination activities is to maximise the impact of the project's outputs. The goal of the project is to widely disseminate the progress and results by a combination of online and offline activities aimed at EMPOWER target groups. Dissemination will also include scientific publications across a range of disciplines, predominantly focused on the FCT domain but also reaching into technical and learning and development domains.

Dissemination activities will inevitably be linked to other activities taking place throughout EMPOWER and will help in meeting three of the six strategic objectives set for the project at the outset.

- SO1. PILOTS. To pilot test a new generation of AI based investigative solutions in the fields of i) visual/image analytics, ii) voice/speech analytics and iii) Federated Learning approach for training AI models. These solutions originate from previously funded R&I projects following a cross-border testing method allowing to assess the effectiveness, performance, usability and compliance with privacy preserving tech in the premises of 2 LEAs in Spain and Portugal.
 - Responds to Activities A1, A2, A3 and A4 of the Call fiche.
 - Addressed in WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5.
 - KPIs: KA1: 8 tools. KA2: 20 staff enrolled. KA3: 1 Evaluation report.

EMPOWER's pilot events will make project results related to the capabilities of the AI solutions available to EU LEA's.

- SO3. DATASETS. To produce and share annotated data sets of anonymised operational data, available to be used by other LEAs and the Security R&I community by the means of the future EU Data Space for Security and Law Enforcement.
 - Responds to Activity B1 of the Call Fiche.
 - Addressed in WP5.
 - KPIs: KB1: 2 datasets.

Disseminating anonymised datasets to allow for exploitation will allow future H2020 and HE projects as well as the Security R&I community to build on the work completed by EMPOWER encouraging ongoing innovations.

- SO4. DISSEMINATION. To disseminate the portfolio of tested and improved solutions ready to be taken up and integrated by LEAs, available at different repositories (EACTDA, Europol) and accompanied by alternative licensing schemes allowing free access to such tools by EU LEAs.
 - Responds to Activity A6, B3, B4, B5 and B6 of the Call Fiche.
 - Addressed in WP5 and WP6.
 - KPIs: KB4: 2 tools adopted by MIR-PN and PJ. KB5: 8 tools available to non-partner LEAs.

Dissemination is, in and of itself, a key SO for EMPOWER. The goal is to ensure there are lasting outputs from this project for stakeholders from a variety of sectors. As identified here, the availability of tools to an extended LEA community is the key focus of dissemination activities within EMPOWER.

The dissemination work of EMPOWER will include *horizon scanning* for suitable events and outlets. This will include relevant conferences and journal special issues on the field. At the same time, there is a widely shared view that trustworthiness and citizen acceptance are important qualities³. This demands wider dissemination efforts through media outlets.

2.3 Exploitation

Exploitation activities, in the context of EMPOWER, will be grouped into two key categories; the uptake of tested solutions by partner LEAs and further uptake of solutions by non-partner LEAs with the cooperation of external stakeholders e.g. EACTDA and Europol Innovation Lab. Exploitation activities will also emphasize the sharing of knowledge and data generated with the aim of enhancing

³ See Marijn Janssen, Paul Brous, Elsa Estevez, Luis S. Barbosa, Tomasz Janowski, Data governance: Organizing data for trustworthy Artificial Intelligence, Government Information Quarterly, Volume 37, Issue 3, 2020, 101493, ISSN 0740-624X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2020.101493>

the skills of LEAs involved in the fight against child sexual exploitation. Effort will be applied to assessing the exploitation pathways and venues leading to the exploitation and adoption of EMPOWER Key Exploitable Results (KER).

Exploitation activities of EMPOWER will contribute to meeting strategic objectives 1 and 2.

- SO2. TRAINING. To perform a training needs assessment, train and provide training material, and curricula recommendations in the use of such novel investigative tools, that might be of the interest of LEA training agencies and organisations (ECTEG, CEPOL, ENLETS).
 - Responds to Activity B1 of the Call Fiche.
 - Addressed in WP4 and WP6.
 - KPIs: KB2: 20 LEA staff trained. KB3: 8 training materials available.

Sharing the TNA, training material and curricula recommendations to a limited audience, i.e. those that will be engaged in using these AI tools for investigative purposes, will increase the speed of adoption. In today's world with ever advancing technological solutions being developed not only by and for LEAs but also by those they are investigating and pursuing it is more important than ever that LEA officials become au fait with solutions available to them in a timely manner. The curricula recommendations developed as part of EMPOWER will acknowledge and incorporate the need for rapid training sessions to reach a level of competence and use alongside sessions that take place over a longer period of time which focus on critical aspects that need to be considered deeply such as the ethical uses of such tools.

2.4 Balanced Scorecard

The EMPOWER balanced scorecard has been amended for a 'best-fit' with the aims and activities of the project. Therefore the four perspectives consist of a traditional financial perspective and internal perspective – highlighting the need to measure success in economic terms and in organisational, or in this case project, processes respectively. EMPOWER has replaced the 'Customer' perspective with an 'End User' perspective demonstrating how LEAs are respected as being part of this process. Finally, in place of a traditional 'Learning and Growth' perspective which focuses on employee development EMPOWER has added an 'Innovation and Learning' perspective emphasizing the value placed on tool innovation and LEA training as part of EMPOWER.

Figure 1: EMPOWER Balanced Scorecard

For the duration of this project, throughout all Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities these four multi-dimensional perspectives will be considered. Communicating successes under each perspective and disseminating and exploiting developments, particularly in the End User and Innovation and Learning perspective will be the focus. By implementing the balanced scorecard framework and reflecting on the four perspectives holistically, EMPOWER will expect a more successful and sustainable outcome from this work⁴⁵.

⁴ Tawse, A. and Tabesh, P., 2023. Thirty years with the balanced scorecard: What we have learned. *Business Horizons*, 66(1), pp.123-132.

⁵ Mio, C., Costantini, A. and Panfilo, S., 2022. Performance measurement tools for sustainable business: A systematic literature review on the sustainability balanced scorecard use. *Corporate social responsibility and environmental management*, 29(2), pp.367-384.

Table 1: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation KPI's

Communication			
Nº	Indicator	Target	Owner
1	Project Identity Handbook	1	TGO
2	Website	1	TGO
3	Average number of visits a month	100	TGO
4	Social media accounts	2	TGO
5	Number of followers	400	TGO
6	Communication materials	2	TGO
7	Press media brief and press releases	7	TGO and PJ and MIRPN
Dissemination			
8	Social media posts	40	All
9	EMPOWER dissemination events	2	PJ and MIR-PN
10	Attendants to EMPOWER events	50	PJ and MIR-PN
11	Events at which EMPOWER has been disseminated	20	All
12	Technical, scientific and academic publications	4	All
Exploitation			
13	Evaluation Report	1	PJ
14	Training materials	8	TGO
15	Annotated Datasets	2	SLG
16	Roadmap for uptake of tools beyond the project	1	PJ and MIR-PN
17	Tools made available to EU law enforcement	8	TGO, VICOM, VOI, HERTA, CERTH and TREBE

3 Target Audience

This plan has been created with specific target groups in mind, mostly composed by the EU Law Enforcement and Internal Security R&I community. At a national level EMPOWER will target LEAs, the national communities for R&I in the Security field, the Community of Users promoted by MIR-PN and the work groups and activities promoted by PJ alongside innovators. The pilot events taking place in Madrid, hosted by MIR-PN, and Lisbon, hosted by PJ, will demonstrate the progress, results and successes of the project.

At EU level, CERIS – the Community for European Research and Innovation for Security and the Fight against Crime and Terrorism, including critical infrastructure protection (FCT/INFRA) thematic area will be specifically targeted to disseminate and demonstrate the pilots' results and LEAs experiences. CERTH and VICOM already participate in the activities and workshops organised by this thematic area due to their project coordinator roles in relevant projects funded by H2020 and HE. ⁶ Participation in the *CERIS community* will afford access to additional LEAs. Stakeholders will also be targeted on the further roll-out of the tools/solutions and in the update of the training materials for LEAs and practitioners. These will include;

- EACTDA (European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association) for demonstration and exploitation purposes. A Demonstration Workshop will be promoted jointly with EACTDA in order to reach and engage non-partner LEAs in the testing of the second cycle of the tools in PJ premises. The portfolio of technology solutions managed by EACTDA will be one of the exploitation venues of the resulting tools. VICOM, MIR-PN, PJ and CERTH are founding members of the association and VICOM is the president of the board and the Spanish Ministry of Interior (ESMIR) is secretary of the board all providing strong pre-existing relationships which EMPOWER can build on.
- Europol: Europol Repository of Tools (ERT) will be one of the exploitation venues assessed in order to make the resulting tools available to other EU LEAs. Europol is a partner of both the GRACE and STARTLIGHT projects, where many EMPOWER partners are also active partners, Hence, EMPOWER has a close links with Europol's Innovation Lab and Europol Cybercrime Centre (EC3). Dissemination will be strengthened through our engagement with; Europol, the EU Innovation Hub for Internal Security, the future EU Centre to prevent and counter child sexual abuse and EMPACT 2022+ Fighting crime together, and the European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services and ENLETS.
- CEPOL (European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Training) and ECTEG (European Cybercrime Training and Education Group): MIR-PN and PJ have close links with both organisations. Moreover, VICOM as Project Coordinator of GRACE is also in contact with ECTEG where some training and awareness raising materials are being adopted to be used in their training programmes. EMPOWER can build on the work of ECTEG taking training materials and curricula recommendations a step further. As far as is possible, EMPOWER will conform to existing practices in terms of the structure of their training materials to ensure ease of use for end users post project.

⁶ For example, see <https://www.starlight-h2020.eu/>

- Relevant H2020 and HE in the Civil Security Field: EMPOWER partners are already part of all the following relevant projects, explicitly mentioned in the Call's fiche, from which EMPOWER is built: GRACE, AIDA, STARLIGHT, INFINITY, CYCLOPES. In the fight against CSEM field, GRACE partners in EMPOWER (CERTH, MIR-PN, PJ and VICOM) have close links with the AVIATOR2 project, co-funded by the Internal Security Fund-Police (ISF-P) programme, also focusing on the prioritization needs for NCMEC reports by LEAs. Moreover, three EMPOWER partners are also engaged with Lessen Data Access and Governance Obstacles (LAGO) project, under Grant Agreement Number 101073951, (Improved access to fighting crime and terrorism research data call), leading to the delivery of a roadmap for the creation of a trusted Data Ecosystem, enabling multiple data spaces for FCT Research. PJ is leading the ENACT Knowledge Network in FCT funded under HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01. VICOM and CERTH are also partners. The Network will start in September with the aim of setting up a Knowledge Network for Security R&I in the Fighting Crime and Terrorism area capable of i) supporting the EU-funded FCT security R&I cycle and the overall community and market actors with actionable evidence, and ii) boosting the Innovation Uptake of the outcomes and results stemming from FCT Security funded R&I projects. Such strong networks also offer opportunities in terms of joint dissemination efforts.

The fight against child sexual exploitation and abuse is a global challenge. Moreover, the R&I community is extended to domain specific stakeholders at world-wide level. EMPOWER will also target this international group of practitioners both within IOs (international organisations) and at the level of the nation state. These bodies play a key role both in terms of raising awareness of CSEM and in terms of providing and disseminating technology solutions. They include: the National Center for Missing and Exploited Children (NCMEC), in US, Project VIC initiative including the ecosystem of VIC Lab tools to fight CSEM, also in the US, the Internet Watch Foundation in UK, and the worldwide network of organisations ECPAT. While the work of EMPOWER will first and foremost focus on networks and collaborative activities within the EU it is important to share the knowledge created beyond EU borders. Additionally, as EMPOWER aims to generate demand for the AI solutions enhanced throughout the project, markets outside the EU need to be considered.

EMPOWER will address the overall R&I community in the Security field composed of the academy, RTOs and industry. The results of EMPOWER should be widely available in order to support knowledge transfer the innovative approach adopted by DIGITAL-2022-DEPLOY-02-LAWSECURITY-AI Call and DIGITAL programme. Our goal is also to overcome the constraints that LEAs face for the deployment and integration of successfully tested tools in R&I projects in their own operational environments and IT systems. In this regard, it should be noted the participation of EMPOWER RTOs, companies and SMEs in relevant networks and associations such as the European Association of Technology and Research Organisations (EARTO) or the European Organisation for Security (EOS) will also be relevant.

Lastly, some of the results from EMPOWER will be more policy oriented. EMPOWER is ultimately addressing key relevant EU wide strategies, which pose some challenges and opportunities, in different fields. EMPOWER will deliver specific learnings and policy recommendations stemming from the innovative approach of EMPOWER in facilitating the deployment (WP4) and uptake of innovative tools by LEAs in three related fields:

- EU Data strategy:⁷ construction of the future EU Data Space for Security and Law Enforcement to be supported by HE and deployed by DIGITAL. As previously mentioned, the participation of many partners in the LAGO project will ensure potential links with the new Data Space. Eventually, EMPOWER will produce anonymised datasets for R&I purposes (not operational data) and results should contribute to such Data Space considering the architecture and interoperability standards agreed by the Data Spaces Support Centre and the EU Data Space for Security and Law Enforcement consortium.
- EU AI strategy: specifically addressing the challenges of the entry into force of the AI Act and its application in order to ensure the ethical aspects related to the Trustworthiness of AI based solutions used for investigative purposes by LEAs.⁸ This socio-ethical element will be provided by ICTLC. Furthermore, CERTH is a member of the AI4LEAs community where EMPOWER results will be disseminated. Both VICOM and CERTH have close links with CENTRIC-Sheffield Hallam University, engaged in the AP4AI Project jointly conducted with Europol and supported by the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA), Eurojust, the EU Agency for Asylum (EUAA) and the EU Agency for Law Enforcement Training (CEPOL) in the framework of the EU Innovation Hub for Internal Security. Links with national AI regulatory sandboxes will also be sought after by partner SMEs in the frameworks created by Portuguese (2020) and Spanish authorities (2022).
- EU fight against CSE: EMPOWER partners will also contribute to building bridges with policymakers, regulators and the future EU Centre to prevent and counter child sexual abuse.

Further to our communication processes, the general public and mass media will also be targeted, mostly to convey the ethical use of AI by LEAs in investigative fields, this in terms of non-discriminatory and non-biased use of AI based models for the delivery of new investigative related solutions and technologies.

⁷ COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A European strategy for data. COM/2020/66 final.

⁸ For an effective summary, see Akhgar, B., Bayerl, P.S., Mounier, G., Linden, R. and Waites, B., 2022. AP4AI: accountability principles for artificial intelligence in the internal security domain. European Law Enforcement Research Bulletin, 22(6).

Table 2: Key Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder	Stake/Interest	KER of Interest	Engagement strategy
CERIS	Methods for effective solution uptake	KER2. Pilot Evaluation Report & Roadmap for Uptake of solutions KER5. Brief with recommendations in Data Interoperability, AI Trustworthiness, and Innovation Uptake models.	Engage through existing network (CERTH, VICOM)
LEAs	Effective solution uptake	KER1. Ethical guidelines for AI Trustworthiness of new generation AI based investigative tools for LEAs KER2. Pilot Evaluation Report & Roadmap for Uptake of solutions KER3. Annotated datasets KER6. Portfolio of AI powered new generation investigative tools including available licensing schemes by non-partner LEAs.	Leverage presence of PJ and MIR-PN
Europol’s Innovation Lab – Europol Tool Repository	Introduction of new digital technologies and intra-agency process among LEAs	KER1. Ethical guidelines for AI Trustworthiness of new generation AI based investigative tools for LEAs KER5. Brief with recommendations in Data Interoperability, AI Trustworthiness, and Innovation Uptake models. KER6. Portfolio of AI powered new generation investigative tools including available licensing schemes by non-partner LEAs.	Engage through existing network (CERTH, VICOM)
EACTDA	Transfer of new tools	KER6. Portfolio of AI powered new generation investigative tools including available licensing schemes by non-partner LEAs.	Relationship established and engagement in line with core mission of EACTDA. ⁹
ECTEG	Training material	KER4. Training needs assessment and materials	Relationship established

⁹ Key activity 5 for EACTDA, “Monitor R&D&I European projects and reach agreements and collaboration frameworks that enable the knowledge of new developments made by those projects; including those that interest the Association in the technological solutions repository.”

3.1 Stakeholder Analysis by Project Phase

Communication, dissemination and exploitation flows will adapt as the project progresses. Two stakeholder analyses maps demonstrating this can be seen below. A typical stakeholder analysis aims to identify all stakeholders, including those that have a low interest in a projects activities and low influence or power over a projects activities. That specific analysis, having been completed prior to the commencement of EMPOWER, will not be included here. Instead this stakeholder analysis focuses solely on key stakeholders of EMPOWER and looks to determine two aspects of the relationship. Firstly, the directionality of interest, i.e. looking to EMPOWER or EMPOWER looking towards them. Secondly this analysis will identify the direction of adoption, that is, is EMPOWER adopting outputs from the identified stakeholder or is the stakeholder adopting outputs and recommendations stemming from the EMPOWER project. Inevitably in the early stages of EMPOWER, as can be seen in Fig. 2, the flow of information will predominantly but not explicitly be from EMPOWER looking to our key stakeholders’ outputs and activities. Additionally, for the most part, EMPOWER will be adopting recommendations from previous stakeholders’ activities and building on these as the project progresses.

Figure 2: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Flows - Early Stages of EMPOWER

What Fig. 3 then demonstrates is how EMPOWER’s and our stakeholder’s perspectives will change as we move to the later stages of the project. In contrast to Fig. 2 here the directionality is predominantly from stakeholders looking to EMPOWERs activities and outputs. This change communicates two key pieces of information relating to EMPOWERs communication strategy. Firstly, the effort EMPOWER needs to exert in order to communicate to our stakeholders the work that is being carried out. Without this initial communication phase stakeholders would be incapable of directing their interest towards these activities. Secondly, it signals how our communication strategy will change in the latter half of the project. As is standard with stakeholder mapping each quadrant signals a different engagement strategy to be adopted. The movement of stakeholders to a new quadrant proposes that a new strategy will be necessary for stakeholder engagement. Engagement is expected to be co-operative and collaborative in the latter stages of the project once demand for the AI solutions has been created.

Figure 3: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Flows - Later Stages of EMPOWER

4 Key Messages and Channels

4.1 Communication

In terms of the overall positioning of this project, EMPOWER bridges the gap between LEAs and R&I community. The objective and messages of the communication strategy will be aimed at showcasing the relevance, impacts and benefits of EMPOWER to the LEA community and R&I community in the FCT field, as well as to the society as a whole.

The following communication tools and activities will be designed and set up during the project:

- Project Identity Handbook: The Visual Identity of the project will comprise a logo and templates for the consistent use of the project logo and the EC logo in all related materials and formats including, but not limited to, reports, deliverables, webpage and social media. The identity will comprise logo, design for webpage, PowerPoint presentation and deliverable templates, project leaflet and other promotional and training materials based on clear style guidelines for online and offline publications.
 - KPI: 1 Project Identity Handbook ready by M03 and used on an ongoing basis until project end.
- Project webpage and social media: A project webpage will be developed (Figure 4) and hosted by TGO's website (it will not be a separate project website) with links to all project partners' websites and sister projects, already referred to¹⁰. LinkedIn (Figure 5) and Twitter (Figure 6) profiles will also be developed and managed to keep stakeholders and target groups informed about the project's progress and results.¹¹

The webpage will provide for a stable environment stakeholders can refer to when looking for information from EMPOWER while the social media pages will cater for more outreach activities where EMPOWER will actively engage and interact with stakeholders, attracting collaborators.

 - KPI: number of website page visits per month, >100; social media follower numbers, > 400. EMPOWERs webpage and social media sites will be developed by M02 and ongoing engagement via social media sites will drive webpage visits during the project.

¹⁰ <https://transgero.eu/empower/>

¹¹ <https://twitter.com/EmpowerPilot/status/1665880180915597313> - this post showed the EMPOWER kick-off meeting.

EMPOWER Preliminary Webpage and Social Media Pages

Figure 5: EMPOWER Webpage

Figure 4: EMPOWER LinkedIn Page

Figure 6: EMPOWER Twitter Page

- Communication materials: Limited use of hard copy materials is proposed, considering the cost and relative impact of such materials: just a leaflet/brochure with basic project information and a roll-up to be used in the pilot networks and events, and in the EMPOWER dissemination events organised.
 - KPI: 1 brochure and roll-up produced.
- Press media brief and press releases: A press media brief will be prepared and used when addressing the mass media with simple and relatable messages about the goals and impact of EMPOWER. Limited press releases will also be issued in key times of the project such as the launch of the Pilot, the implementation of the cross-border pilot activities with the participation of both PJ and MIR-PN in a single location and the dissemination of the project's recommendations.
 - KPI: 1 press brief produced, delivered to >10 mass media; press releases issued >6.

4.2 Dissemination

The effective dissemination of the project's progress and results will be an on-going priority phased activity. It will revolve around the following facets of the project, conveying specific messages aimed at different target groups. There are four key themes EMPOWER's dissemination activities will be grouped under, Progress in Technology, Training Needs, Ethical Compliance and Innovation.

Dissemination will reflect the structure of the overall project whereby throughout EMPOWER solutions will be tested, evaluations and feedback will be provided, and enhancements will be applied in order to improve their performance, usability and effectiveness. This in turn will benefit LEAs investigations targeting the broad EU R&I community, such as CoUs, CERIS and Europol's Innovation Lab. Progress will also be made on interoperability and in the development of new standards in the data sharing domain with research and investigative purposes.

One of the key output of the EMPOWER project will be a Training Needs Analysis in relation to the adoption of AI based tools in LEAs. This will be disseminated across EU LEAs and related bodies including EACTDA, ECTEG and Europol. This TNA will specifically identify cross border common requirements in LEA's for the purpose of building capacity around using such tools. This dissemination will target the EU wide ecosystem of agencies engaged in the training of LEAs, such as CEPOL, ECTEG, EMPACT+.

The EMPOWER training piece will include ethical compliance of the proposed AI based tools and their ethical trustworthiness. This will target EC policymakers, regulators, and initiatives working towards the advancement of the use of AI by LEAs.

To sum up, the following dissemination channels and activities will be used:

- Ongoing dissemination of progress and results by the project website and social media, by the means of disseminating the public deliverables of the project, including lay / easy to follow briefs in the 4 referred fields.
 - KPI: Project news posted about project progress and results: 40; project briefs reported and delivered on website: 4.
- Organization of EMPOWER dissemination events aiming at all the target groups, both at national and EU level. EMPOWER will organise at 2 workshops for disseminating project results: i) a dissemination workshop in Spain, by MIR-PN, in cooperation with the national Community of Users of Spain; and ii) a cross-border Demonstration and Dissemination event, in Lisbon, organised by PJ in cooperation with EACTDA, with the participation of LEAs and target groups from all over Europe.
 - KPI: EMPOWER dissemination workshops: 2. Attendants: 50 people in all workshops (this may include an on-line option)
- The participation at other events organised by target groups will also be promoted by all partners: the participation in at least one CERIS Workshop in FCT/INFRA Thematic Area is expected, as well as participation at events organised by still running sister projects such as STARLIGHT and LAGO, other successful proposals under the DIGITAL-2022-DEPLOY-02-LAW-SECURITY-AI - Security (law enforcement): AI-based pilot Call and other initiatives promoted by DIGITAL in the domain of AI and Data Spaces in the Security and Law Enforcement field, such as UNICRI – INTERPOL conference on AI and Robotics for Policing; Europol-ENISA AI /IoT Security conference; EMPACT - European multidisciplinary platform against criminal threats; Council of the EU's Law Enforcement Workgroup, the European Network of Forensics Science Institutes meeting, etc.
 - KPI: participation in congresses and conferences, >10; participation in local, regional, or national events for LEA >10
- Technology partners and practitioners will disseminate the project results in limited scientific and technological publications, following open science practices. EMPOWER will ensure a 'green' open access strategy for scientific publications and where feasible, open access publishing ('gold' open access) will be selected for dissemination in relevant scientific journals. To that end EMPOWER will target technology-oriented journals as well as forensics and practitioners oriented publications. Amongst others, these include: Research Policy; ACM Transactions on Interactive Intelligent Systems; International Journal of Multimedia Information Retrieval; Multimedia Tools and Applications; European Law Enforcement Research Bulletin; SIAK - Journal (Journal for Police Science and Practice); IEEE Security and Privacy; Digital Investigation; European Journal of Criminology; Internet Journal of Criminology; Journal of Child Sexual Abuse.
 - KPI: number of publications in technical, scientific, and academic journals, target >4

4.3 Exploitation

EMPOWER project leverages and integrates research results funded by the EC into the day-to-day practice of EU LEAs. The exploitation strategy will be devoted to defining and implementing the best pathways and channels leading to the exploitation and adoption of EMPOWER Key Exploitable Results (KER) by target groups. To that end EMPOWER will deliver the following Key Exploitable Results:

Table 3 EMPOWER Key Exploitable Results

Nº	KER	Target group/s
1	KER1. Ethical guidelines for AI Trustworthiness of new generation AI based investigative tools for LEAs	EC, Europol, EU Innovation Hub for Internal Security, popAI and AP4AI projects, LEAs, Industry, RTOs
2	KER2. Pilot Evaluation Report & Roadmap for Uptake of solutions	EC, Europol, CERIS, CoU, LEAs, Industry, RTOs
3	KER3. Annotated datasets	LEAs, EU Data Space for Research in FCT, Data Space for Security and Law Enforcement
4	KER4. Training needs assessment and materials	LEAs, Europol, CEPOL, ECTEG
5	KER5. Brief with recommendations in Data Interoperability, AI Trustworthiness, and Innovation Uptake models.	CoU, CERIS, EOS, DEP’s Common Data Support Centre, Europol, EU Innovation Hub for Internal Security
6	KER6. Portfolio of AI powered new generation investigative tools including available licensing schemes by non-partner LEAs.	LEAs, Europol, EACTDA, CERIS, ENLETS

There are four principal channels to be used to successfully exploit these results.

Policy: Firstly, the intended exploitation pathway for KER 1, 2, 4 and 5 will be the uptake of EMPOWER recommendations by policymakers within the EU. In addition, the R&I community to build on the work of EMPOWER having also adopted the recommendations that are made as part of this project.

Transfer of Data: The second pathway, to achieve KER 3, is to have the annotated datasets, created by EMPOWER, transferred to open repositories where they will be accessible by the key target groups identified above.

Scientific Publications: KER's 1 and 4 can be exploited through the dissemination of knowledge generation via scientific and technical publications. Innovative approaches and processes can be shared directly with R&I communities as with EU bodies mentioned above via open access databases.

Demonstration Events: Live demonstration events, hosted both by MIR-PN and by PJ will be a key source of exploitation as the tools and solutions deployed and tested during EMPOWER will be seen in action by LEAs outside of this project. Similarly, this will be a key pathway to demonstrating tools leading to the dissemination of licenses via EACTDA and Europol.

Overall, the EMPOWER project will increase the performance of EU LEAs by the uptake of innovative investigative tools, increasing the performance of LREAs in the fight against crime and terrorism including CSE.

5 Planned Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Budget

Dissemination efforts will be focused on potential end-users of EMPOWER outputs and channels to reach and engage these end-users. Impact will be the driver of how EMPOWER will target dissemination. Thus, resources will be closely aligned to the strategic goals.

In order to remain efficient and act in an economical manner consortium partners intend to communicate and disseminate many aspects of this project through channels that may not incur any costs. Digital brochures will be used when possible and consortium meetings will be planned to coincide with times and locations of events that many partners are expected to attend. If a highly relevant event is taking place within a country that a partner resides, every effort will be taken to ensure the local partners represent EMPOWER.

That said, it is inevitable that costs will be incurred in order to communicate, disseminate and exploit the work of the EMPOWER project to the fullest degree. Aspects that will incur costs include limited printing of promotional material, travel and event participation expenses, bilateral meetings with potential final users and fees associated with ensuring scientific publications are openly accessible. Finally, the two key demonstration events that EMPOWER intends to host at MIRPN and PJ will involve some financial output. The requirements of Article 17, including Annex 5, will be respected throughout the project. The visibility of EU funding will be ensured when communicating and disseminating project-related information at all times.

Partners will each take responsibility for communicating with stakeholders in their own space, for example ICTLC will visit the Maastricht European Centre on Privacy and Cybersecurity, SLG will attend the EBDVF, VOI will attend the Web Summit and TREBE will attend USEC.

Given the difficulty in providing specific costings for travel and registration fees and predicting the journals that will accept scientific publications the planned budget is currently an estimate

Communication	
Printing materials	€1,000
Dissemination	
Conference and Event Participation and Attendance	€32,000
Demonstrations	€6,000
Exploitation	
Bilateral Meetings, Conferences, Event Attendance and Participation	€8,000
Estimated Budget Plan	€47,000

6 Conclusion

Working on the successful roll-out of novel AI tools to the European law enforcement community is a challenge that requires an interdisciplinary approach. This is a complex area with a diverse array of stakeholders. Thus, communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies require careful curation. Such strategies need to be mindful of the *security* of participants, the sensitive nature of many of the EMPOWER deliverables, the importance of citizen buy-in and indeed IP regimes and commercial imperatives of tool developers.

Well-designed communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies are key to ensuring legacy for projects like EMPOWER. This is a key attribute of any successful EC funded project. EMPOWER will seek to leave a tangible legacy through the dissemination of knowledge and the development of training material. This latter point can be underestimated, in this domain both technical training and training on the *capabilities* of digital technologies is critical. Hence, training efforts should not be confined to narrow cohorts of LEA personnel but should be inclusive in its orientation.

In terms of the uptake of tools and innovative technologies, there are a number of *innovation brokers* in this domain, these include communities of users, CERIS and EACTDA. These organisations and other similar institutions are key stakeholders in communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts of the EMPOWER team.

Overall, EMPOWER will seek to maximise impact through engaging with a variety of stakeholders from practitioners to policy-makers. EMPOWER aims to make a tangible contribution in terms of tool deployment – and our communication and dissemination strategy will strive to ensure that effective tools in the fight against CSE are rolled out within the EU

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